

Myricetin-3',4',7-trimethyl ether from the leaves of *Premna tomentosa*

K. Balakrishna^a, E. Sukumar^a, Sarada Vasanth^{a*} and A. Patra^b

^aCentral Research Institute for Siddha (CCRAS), Arumbakkam, Chennai-600 106, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, University College of Science, 92, A. P. C. Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : saradavasanth@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-44-26214809

Manuscript received 7 January 2003, accepted 21 March 2003

Chemical investigation of the leaves of *Premna tomentosa* afforded myricetin-3',4',7-trimethyl ether from the benzene insoluble fraction of the methanol extract.

P. tomentosa Willd. (Verbenaceae) is a medium-size tree distributed in Madhya Pradesh, Northern Circars, Deccan and Carnatic down to South Travancore in deciduous forests upto a height of 4000 ft. The oil from the roots is aromatic and used as a remedy for stomach disorders. In Siddha system of medicine, this plant is known as *Pidangunari* and the decoction of the leaves is used as a stomachic¹.

No detailed work has been done on this plant other than the isolation of a flavone-C-glycoside (vicenin-3) from the heartwood and a study on the antihepatotoxic and antioxidant properties of the leaf extract in albino rats². In this communication, we report the isolation of myricetin-3',4',7-trimethyl ether (3,5,5'-trihydroxy-3',4',7-trimethoxyflavone) (1) from the leaves of *P. tomentosa*. This compound has earlier been isolated from the oil secreted by the buds of *Aesculus hippocastanum* Linn. (Sapindaceae) and characterized³.

Shade-dried and coarsely powdered leaves of *P. tomentosa* (2.0 kg) collected from in and around Chennai city was extracted with methanol in cold (72 h) and fractionated into benzene soluble and insoluble portions. The latter fraction (35 g) was column chromatographed over silica gel (100–200 mesh) and eluted with solvents of increasing polarity. Elution of the column with benzene-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) afforded compound 1, purified by crystallization from ethyl acetate, m.p. 230–232°, R_f 0.58 in chloroform-methanol (19 : 1) and gave blue-green ferric chloride reaction as well as positive Shinoda test for flavonoid. The structure 1 elucidated was based on its IR, UV, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral information of its triacetate, 3,5,5'-triacetoxy-3',4',7-trimethoxyflavone (2). Due to solubility problem, the triacetate 2 (m.p. 223–225°) was considered for NMR studies which was prepared by heating 1 with acetic anhydride-sodium acetate on an oil-bath for 2 h. Compound 1 : λ_{max} (MeOH) 256, 362; +NaOAc 255, 365; +NaOAc and H₃BO₃ 259, 366; +AlCl₃ 273, 445; +AlCl₃

and HCl 270, 408; +NaOMe 294, 421 nm (with decrease in intensity of band I); ν_{max} (KBr) 3419, 2945, 2854, 1657, 1591, 1505, 1438, 1362, 1214, 1158, 1098, 1036, 909, 838, 792 cm⁻¹. Compound 2 : δ_H (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) 6.60 (1H, d, J 2.2 Hz, H-6), 6.80 (1H, d, J 2.2 Hz, H-8), 7.50 (1H, d, J 1.7 Hz, H-6'), 7.68 (1H, d, J 1.7, H-2'), 2.33, 2.33, 2.46 (3H each, s, 3 × OAc), 3.82 (3H, s, 1 × OMe), 3.90 (3H, s, 1 × OMe), 3.91 (3H, s, 1 × OMe); δ_C (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) 157.8 (C-2), 134.0 (C-3), 173.0 (C-4), 150.8 (C-5), 108.3 (C-6), 163.8 (C-7), 98.8 (C-8), 163.8 (C-9), 108.7 (C-10), 128.6 (C-1'), 110.3 (C-2'), 152.4 (C-3'), 143.7 (C-4'), 141.9 (C-5'), 115.5 (C-6'), 56.0 (7-OCH₃), 56.5 (3'-OCH₃), 60.3 (4'-OCH₃), 169.3, 167.6, 167.2 (3 × OCOCH₃), 21.0, 20.7, 20.5 (3 × OCOCH₃).

This is the second report on the occurrence of this flavonoid in nature and first from family Verbenaceae.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Director, Central Council for Research in Ayurveda and Siddha (CCRAS), New Delhi and the Assistant Director-in-Charge, Central Research Institute for Siddha, Chennai for facilities, encouragement and support. They also thank Dr. S. Usman Ali, former Head, Department of Pharmacognosy, C.R.I.(S) for the identification of the plant material.

References

1. R. N. Chopra, S. L. Nayar and I. C. Chopra, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1999, p. 203; K. S. Murugesha Mudaliar, "Siddha Materia Medica", Department of Indian Medicine and Homoeopathy, Government of Tamil Nadu, Chennai, 1998, p. 675.
2. D. Jyotsana, P. N. Sarma, G. Srimannarayana and A. V. S. Rao, *Curr. Sci.*, 1984, **53**, 573; K. P. Devi, R. Anandan, T. Devaki, T. Apparannantham and K. Balakrishna, *Biomed. Res.*, 1998, **19**, 339.
3. E. Wollenwaber and K. Egger, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1970, **19**, 1601.